

CORSA DEEP EARTH OBSERVATION SEMANTIC COMPRESSION APPLIED TO FLOOD DETECTION

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CONTENT

1 – CORSA

2 – SEMANTIC SEGMENTATION EXERCICE

CORSA

Auto-Encoders

CORSA: VQ-VAE3 FPN

Usability of CORSA

CORSA: Compression

SSIM = 0.956
PSNR = 13.724
MSE = 8915.57
CR (uint16) = 24.36

Original RGB

Original NIR

CORSA: Compression

SSIM = 0.956
PSNR = 13.724
MSE = 8915.57
CR (uint16) = 24.36

Reconstructed RGB

Reconstructed NIR

A large white outline of a water drop is positioned on the left side of the slide, set against a solid green background. The drop is filled with a pattern of horizontal white lines of varying lengths, suggesting water or a liquid surface.

FLOOD DETECTION

2100 120x120x4 px patches were selected for the training and validation datasets.

The maximal overlap between tiles was set to 80% and 90% of the patches were required to comprise water pixels.

For the latter, the minimal fraction of water pixels was set at 0.5%.

Flood Detection dataset

Semantic Segmentation

- conv2d, kernel_size=3, padding='same'
- ↓ maxpool pool_size=2
- ↑ upsampling size=2
- concatenate
- conv2d, kernel_size=2, padding='same'

Reconstruction Effects

raw

reconstructed

Algorithm	Metrics			Weight (in parameters)	Input type
	Jaccard	Precision	Recall		
NDWI	55.8%	96.2%	56.3%	0	Original Image
U-Net	70.2%	83.2%	82.1%	353 665	Original Image
Reconstruction + U-Net	70.3%	82.6%	82.4%	1 212 165	CORSA Representations

AI on CORSA representations

AI on CORSA representations

Naïve network

Hierarchical network

Algorithm	Metrics			Weight (in parameters)	Input type
	Jaccard	Precision	Recall		
Decoder + U-Net	70.3%	81.6%	83.5%	1 212 165	CORSA representations
Crow-Net	71.4%	81.6%	85.2%	1 791 165	CORSA representations
Shrike-Net	72.2%	83.8%	83.8%	3 168 345	CORSA representations

Future Works

- CORSA focuses on structures, the distribution is therefore different from the original input. It might be worth correcting this effect if the compression ratio is only mildly affected.
- Applying CORSA on L0 and L1 products (simulations)
- Testing various compression ratios for various applications

THANK YOU

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